

SOFT LEADERSHIP AND ITS IMPACT ON THE PERFORMANCE OF BUSINESS ORGANIZATIONS “A SAMPLE SURVEY OF ADMINISTRATIVE LEADERS WORKING IN COMMERCIAL BANKS IN BAGHDAD”

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Abstract

Aim of Study: The study aims primarily to identify the impact of soft leadership and its dimensions on business organizations of trade banks in Baghdad. **The problem of the Study:** The study presents an essential question: Does the soft leadership has an impact on the business organizations performance in the field of banking the subject of the study. **The Research Curriculum:** To fulfil the aim of the study, a descriptive analytical method is used and a questionnaire survey is prepared to collect the required data which is considered as a measurement tool to the study. The questionnaire survey was disseminated to a random excerpt which was collected randomly according to Stephen Thompson equation of the study culture which is comprised of administrative leadership working in trade banks in Baghdad. The number of the culture selected were 118. For the purpose of testing the stud hypothesis, a collection of statistical methods were adapted and statistical software SPSS (v.25) and AMOS were utilized. **Conclusion:** The soft leadership variable has a major and an essential impact on the business organizations performance of the banks (the study culture).

Keywords: Soft Leadership, Business Organizations performance.

INTRODUCTION:

The banks’ managers require the hard and soft leadership characteristics in order to achieve the organization’s goals. It is not adequate for banks managers to rely solely on their administrative and knowledge in running their banking establishments especially in a time where the globalization and rapid development take effect on the global banking systems. They in grave need of leadership traits that may enable them encourage staff and employees and to develop the banking services in return and the constant improvement to cope with the advancement in the banking market, and to guarantee that the employees are readied to face possible challenges and change. (Ngang, 2015:332). Soft leadership is considered fairly new concept that was presented by (Roa) for the first time in 2012, where He thinks that soft leadership is an essential condition to a modern and interconnected globe. The concept is put into practice throughout the application of individuals’ soft skills. He stressed that the soft leadership is a modal for complete leadership, and that participation, relations and behavior that is used for negotiations, persuasions, appreciation, motivation and other corporation tools used to directing individuals

to perform their tasks effectively (Gholami, 2017:322). AL-Hjaj argued that leadership has seven traits that helps to establish an effective leader in his generation that can bring a change to their current situation of the organization and in general. These traits are (Clear prospectus, courage, and self-motivation, ability to persuade others, true and complete knowledge of each staff member). He generate a plan for the organization that cares for everyone's interest, commitment and/or follow up. The acting leader on daily tasks (Processing Leader) does not do that. Having a vision and plan generating for the organization are considered tasks can only be done by a leader who is able to bring a change to the current situation and makes it better and a leader can transcend to what is beyond the daily tasks and works on a higher level, where he can affect the individuals' culture, which means the change in the way of thinking that can lead to creativity and development (AL-Hajaj, 2014:12). Soft leadership combines soft skills and hard skills. These skills ought to be taken into consideration by the leader and paying attention to the significance and value of the human resources with the ability to produce and manage feelings successfully. Which means that the leader's main focus is on the individuals not the tasks where he shows compassion with others and look at things from a human prospectus. The soft leadership concentrate on the individualism of people, their attitudes and behavior, where it encourages to making others think highly of themselves (AL-Hadrawi and Jalal, 2020:210). The performance concept on the other hand includes different criterion in addition to proficiency and effectiveness like cycling rates, accidents, absence, late and sloth. The good working individual is characterized by his high productivity and his performance contributes to lessen work related issues (Ababs, 1999).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

1. The Problem of Study:

Organizations at the current and future stage in Iraq in general and civil banks in particular, need leaders with scientific qualifications and competencies, due to the nature of competition and expected economic growth, especially if foreign investments enter the banking sector, as many economists and bankers expect that problems and challenges will increase not because of the lack of management leadership, but because of the lack of qualifications, skills and knowledge they are starting to use, and it is clear that the environment of Iraqi banks has not enjoyed leadership practices. Soft compared to the studies that global banks have received in the field of banking business, which confirms the need for these banks to sample research to prove their position and look for formulas and practices that draw their objectives and through which workers feel that they are part of this organization, and the problem of research can be formulated in the main question: Is there an impact of soft leadership on the performance of banks from the point of view of the research sample?

2. Aims of Study:

The study aims at achieving certain goals that can be summarized as follows:

- a. To identify the availability of the dimensions of current research variables represented by the following variables (soft leadership, performance of business organizations) in the banks of the research sample.
- b. Learn about the role of soft leadership and its impact on the performance of business organizations.
- c. Identify the levels of direct impact between search variables and their subdivisions in the search sample banks.
- d. Learn about the level of impact of soft leadership on the performance of business organizations in selected banks.

3. Significance of the Study:

The current research provides an intellectual discussion of topics of great importance at the administrative levels and have a great role to improve the performance of private banks in Iraq and the research acquires its importance from the nature of the selected variables and the field researched:

- a. The current research combines two important topics in the field of management and economics, namely, the independent changer, soft leadership, and the variable of the performance of business organizations.
- b. This research contributes to enriching the Iraqi Scientific Library, which specializes in business management topics in Iraqi organizations, especially the banking sector, and seeking to communicate with the efforts of researchers in the efforts of researchers to provide topics that are addressed intellectually and cognitively.
- c. Encourage the administrative leaders working in the banking field to learn about the importance of research variables and benefit from them and to give the employees of the bank their opinions and encourage them to improve their giving and thereby improve banking performance.

4. Hypothetical Research :

Fig 1: Hypothesis Research Sample

5. **Research hypotheses:** The first major hypothesis (H1): "There is a morally significant effect of soft driving and its combined dimensions in the performance of business organizations from the point of view of the members of the research sample."
6. The research community was the administrative leaders and their aides and the heads of departments and administrative units working in the following banks (Gulf Commercial Bank, Mosul Development and Investment Bank, Iraqi Union Bank, Ashur International Bank, Mansour Investment Bank, Bank across Iraq, Al Huda Bank, Development Bank) working in Baghdad, and the 250 individuals who were selected from them a random sample of (150) individuals and table (1) explaining the research community and the sample and how to calculate it:

Table -1- Research Community sample						
No	Name of Bank	Size of Community	Size of Culture	No. Retrieved Survey	Date of Establishment	Geographical Location
1	Gulf Commercial Bank	17	10	10	2000	Baghdad/Sadoon St.
2	Mosul Bank for Development and Investment	20	12	10	2001	Baghdad/Karrada-AL-Nidhal St.
3	Union Bank of Iraq	52	31	21	2004	Baghdad/ALMasbah Sq.
4	Ashur International Bank	56	33	20	2005	Baghdad/ Uqba Bin Nafe Sq.
5	Al-Mansour Investment Bank	32	20	16	2007	Baghdad/ Karrada Kharig
6	Trans-Iraq Bank	28	17	15	2006	Baghdad/ALOlwiya
7	AL-Huda Bank	15	9	9	2008	Baghdad-Karrada/Hay AL-Wahda
8	International Development Bank	30	18	17	2011	Baghdad/ Arsat AL-hindiyah

Second: Theoretical Framework

1. Soft Leadership

a. The concept of Soft Leadership:

Soft leadership requires a very high degree of personal skills to work with others, gently motivate others to carry out their commitments with all energy and passion, and encourage others to work together towards achieving the leader's vision and this is done only through the belief of individuals in their leader, vision and follow-up to achieve the same goal, "personal skills" can be seen as the behaviors shown by the leader while dealing with individuals according to kolzow professional attitudes, 2014:127)). A soft leader is the one who motivates individuals to improve individual or organization-level performance and here uses soft soft skills to effectively raise the organization's success through its own charisma, more praise, motivation, inspiration, and individual thinking. These soft skills of a soft leader are usually the difference between a regular leader and a great leader who inspires and positively influences them to develop their abilities and accomplish tasks in a shorter and less dangerous time, focusing on the nature of learning and continuous development (Aman, 2016:12).Soft leadership was defined as "a kind of leadership that engages emotional intelligence with management and aims to create existing human visions to build characters that transcend their boundaries of knowledge, through participatory complementary relationships" (Zabaniotou,2021:3).

b. The significance of Soft Leadership

The importance of soft leadership lies in the practice of cooperation, trust and kindness and not to follow the style of control that is no longer important at the moment, especially as we live in an open world that is rapidly changing and this change in turn affects the change of jobs, skills and abilities of employees as it is necessary to keep pace with the change that has taken place and provide modern leadership solutions through the modernity that has obtained tools and techniques and their use towards their employees (Ajil, 2019:11). The importance of soft leadership is manifested in: (sadj, 2019:31) and has been explained by (Ali, 42:2020).

- Soft skills are the basic basis of leadership within the organization because they give individuals the ability to manage and organize their time more effectively and this leads to reducing stress and enhancing job loyalty, thus becoming more productive.
- Soft leadership helps to reduce conflict within the organization and thus reduces the recourse to organizational policies and reduces the level of obstacles facing the organization.
- Soft leadership focuses on individuals and works to empower them to reduce attrition in the workplace.
- Working on positive change for individuals within the organization, through trust and mutual cooperation to reduce personal resistance and uncertainty.

c. Measuring Soft Leadership:

Soft leadership can be measured by the following dimensions:

- **vision:** those trends or perceptions of the future of the organization and what it should be in the distant future, i.e. a picture of the future of the organization and from which the goals are determined and the vision must be consistent with the principles and values of the organization, and on the basis of this vision is worked on a daily basis by the leader and other individuals to achieve the strategic goals sought by the organization (Ahmed, 2020:10).
- **Communication:** As an inspiration and encouragement of an individual or group through systematic and targeted sharing of information using excellent communication skills, especially in light of the current rapid progress and change, the biggest challenge these days is how to gain the trust of the organization's employees and customers. With leaders who are skilled enough to communicate significantly and distinctively with well-planned and customized communication policies, the organization helps encourage not only employees, but also partners and customers to make them trust the organization. (Johansson et al, 2011:3).
- **Emotional intelligence:** It is the mixed model that combines in one personality the social behaviors and competencies of a leader that help him to exercise his soft leadership and achieve cooperation by building long and stable relationships to build an integrated team (Ajil, 2019: 13).

2. The performance of business organizations:

a. The concept of the performance of business organizations is an essential concept for business organizations in general and is considered the focus of the attention of management scientists and is almost a comprehensive phenomenon and a central element of all branches of science and fields of management knowledge including the management of the organization and means performance as the ability of the institution to survive, adapt and grow within the framework of the strategic objectives it seeks to achieve and comes first of all strategic success (Abu Qahf, 1993: 93). The term performance continues to provoke controversy, debate and differences in the opinions of researchers, due to differing thesis, opinions and developments in the nature of performance based on environmental and technical variables, resource use and multiple dimensions of performance due to its organizational importance. Knowledge is managed within the Matrix Management Matrix (2016: 67). Input ratio Efficiency and effectiveness, a good worker is highly productive and his performance contributes to reducing work-related problems (Mersal and Massoud, 2020: 387-388).

b. Performance levels of business organizations: There are many levels of performance through which the organization can recognize its performance level: (Shane, 2017:108), (AL-Hassan, 2014: 34-35).

- **Exceptional performance:** it shows excellence in performance within the industry at the moment, in the long run and lucrative contracts, as well as demonstrates the commitment of individuals and shows the abundance of liquidity and the prosperity of the organization's financial situation
- **Outstanding performance:** This is demonstrated by leading the industry, as well as obtaining a large set of employment contracts, having highly efficient and stimulating frameworks, and providing a distinctive financial and monetary position. Very good performance: shown through solidity in performance, clarity of vision for the future as well as efficient frameworks as well as good financial position.
- **Very good performance:** it appears through solid performance, clarity of future vision, in addition to efficient frameworks, in addition to enjoying a good financial position.
- **Good performance:** It shows the excellence of performance according to the prevailing performance rates with the balance of strengths and weaknesses in products, services, customer base and frameworks, in addition to owning a stable financial situation.
- **Moderate performance:** The fact that performance is below average, and that weaknesses overcome the strengths of products, services, customer base and frameworks .in addition to the difficulty of gaining the adequate finance of sustainability and growth.
- **Poor performance:** Here represents a performance that is much below average, with weaknesses clearly visible in almost all axes, in addition to serious difficulties in attracting qualified frameworks, while facing serious financial problems.

- **Distressed performance:** This is a completely inefficient performance, and is likely to cause major and varied problems in all aspects and axes of the organization's work.

C. Measuring the performance of business organizations:

The most important dimensions of the quality of financial services that will be addressed in this research can be explained:

- **learning and growth:** this dimension focuses on how the organization learns to create and achieve more effective value for the customer, by providing new products and services, as a result of improving the efficiency and effectiveness of the internal processes of the institution, after learning and growing the process of renewal as the main factor of survival and permanence, i.e. training workers and unifying their cultural positions to develop the organization in accordance with environmental changes, and encouraging them to develop themselves in a way that Permanent (Al Hassan, 2014: 53).
- **Internal operations:** Internal operations mean all internal activities and events that distinguish the organization from other organizations, through which the needs of customers and the objectives of the owners are interviewed, and therefore the measures associated with the internal processes of the balanced performance card are supposed to emanate from processes that have an impact on customer satisfaction and the techniques required to ensure the progress of the market leadership line and must decide what processes are supposed to excel or distinguish them, and this dimension focuses on the work of the organization and how to achieve excellence Which distinguishes it over other organizations in the market (Shin, 2017: 153).
- **Financial performance:** Gaining appropriate financial results is essential for the survival and growth of economic organizations, and measuring and analyzing financial results is one of the necessary elements to examine the strengths and weaknesses within the organization, i.e. financial indicators are an essential component of a balanced performance card in organizations, whether profitable or not, i.e. the main objective of the financial perspective is to maximize profits by maximizing the benefits to shareholder investors (Alijan, 2021: 77).
- **Customers:** This dimension contains goals related to satisfying customers, such as achieving the wishes of customers through new services and products, responding to complaints submitted by them, improving the method of sale and service, as well as increasing knowledge of the products and services of the organization, that is, helps to cover a significant deficiency in organizations, requires business organizations at the moment, to put the requirements, needs and desires of customers at the heart of their strategies, because of the great importance this is reflected in the success of the organization in its competition with other competing organizations, its survival and continuity Its activity in the market depends on its ability to provide products of high quality and reasonable prices, and through this perspective managers are able to translate their organization's message regarding customers to all over the world (Kabil, 2009: 226).

Third: Practical Framework of the Study:

1. **Stability:** The stability refers to the inner integrity of the measurement which means that all questions serve a general purpose that is subject to measurement and possibility of having the same results is the same when the same measurement is used once again (Oppenheim, 1992, p: 144). The survey can be clarified through utilizing Alpha Kronback measurement tool which is considered one of the most stable measurements tools in the practical realm. Table -2- illustrates the results of Alpha Kronback.

Table -2- Cronbach's alpha			
Primary variables	Dimensions	No. of questions	Cronbach's alpha
Soft leadership	Vision	5	0.852
	Connection	5	0.836
	Emotional intelligence	5	0.838
Business Organizations Performance	Learning and growth	5	0.878
	Inner operations	5	0.826
	Financial performance	5	0.869
	customers	5	0.825

Table (2) shows that alpha Cronbach's values ranging from (0.826-0.878) to the variables and dimensions of the research, which are greater than 0.70), this indicates that variables and dimensions have an appropriate internal consistency, and these results indicate that the study scale (questionnaire) has a good level of stability, and evidence of the extent to which the scale can be repeated and the results themselves given, so other statistical tests can be performed based on these results.

2. Constructive honesty

- a. is a soft driving model: Figure 2 illustrates the soft driving model, which consists of three basic dimensions and a reality (15) questions and each after five questions.

Fig 2: Complete sample of the soft leadership

Table 3 shows that the standard saturation values of all soft driving variable questions ranged from (0.605-0.821), which is a good relative, as the standard saturation values indicate the extent to which each question contributes to its dimension, the higher the contribution of the question, the more important it is to explain the dimension to which it belongs. The results show that the constructive honesty of the scale of all the questions of the soft driving variable is moral, as it turns out that the standard values (C.R) for all questions ranged from (6.195-9.359) and are greater than the critical standard value (C.R) of (1.96), which indicates the sincerity of the questions, which is a good indicator for subsequent statistical analyses. The value of the indication level for all soft driving variable questions at (0.000) is lower than the semantic level (0.05), which also indicates that all questions are moral and is a good indicator.

Table (3) shows the statistical indicators for soft leadership sample

P	Dimensions	STANDARD SATURATION	C.R	Path	Questions
	Vision	0.777		V1	<---
0.000		.821	9.359	V2	<---
0.000		0.742	8.304	V3	<---
0.000		0.705	7.829	V4	<---
0.000		.605	6.576	V5	<---
	Connection	.659		C1	<---
0.000		.829	7.584	C2	<---
0.000		.643	6.195	C3	<---
0.000		.686	6.556	C4	<---
0.000		.736	6.952	C5	<---
	Emotional intelligence	.809		EI1	<---
0.000		.627	6.877	EI2	<---
0.000		.754	8.548	EI3	<---
0.000		.681	7.579	EI4	<---
0.000		.690	7.701	EI5	<---

B. Business Organization Performance Model: Figure 3 shows the performance model of business organizations, which consists of four basic dimensions and consists of (20) questions with five questions per dimension

Figure 3: Complete sample the performance model of business organizations

It is clear from table (4) that the standard saturation values of all business organization performance variable questions ranged from (0.422-0.834), which is a good relative, as the standard saturation values indicate the extent to which each question contributes to the dimension to which it belongs, the higher the contribution of the question, the more important it is to explain the dimension to which it belongs. The results indicated that the constructive honesty of the measure of all questions variable performance of business organizations moral, as it was found that the standard values (CR) of all questions ranged from (4.361- 8.691) which is greater than the critical standard value (CR) of (1.96), which indicates the sincerity of the phrases, which is a good indicator for the conduct of subsequent statistical analyses. The value of the level of indication for all questions of the variable performance of business organizations (0.000) is lower than the level of indication (0.05) and this also indicates that all questions are moral and indicate the sincerity of the phrases, which is a good indicator.

Table (4) shows the statistical indicators of business organizations performance sample

P	Dimensions	STANDARD SATURATION	C.R	Path	Questions
	Learning and growth	.736		LAG1	<---
0.000		.743	7.837	LAG2	<---
0.000		.821	8.691	LAG3	<---
0.000		.765	8.078	LAG4	<---
0.000		.777	8.216	LAG5	<---
	Inner operations	.694		IO1	<---
0.000		.705	7.066	IO2	<---
0.000		.691	6.935	IO3	<---
0.000		.757	7.557	IO4	<---
0.000		.640	6.454	IO5	<---
	Financial performance	.696		FP1	<---
0.000		.710	7.090	FP2	<---
0.000		.834	8.213	FP3	<---
0.000		.736	7.330	FP4	<---
0.000		.796	7.884	FP5	<---
	Customers	.729	7.972	CO1	<---
		.820		CO2	<---
0.000		.721	7.878	CO3	<---
0.000		.756	8.286	CO4	<---
0.000		.422	4.361	CO5	<---

3. Statistical analysis of variables:

The results shown in Table (5) showed that the highest total arithmetic mean was at the variable (performance of business organizations) as it reached (3.62) and with a good level and standard deviation of (0.473) and a coefficient of difference of (13.039) where the percentage of agreement on this variable (72.484%) while the disagreement reached the percentage (27.516%), as this variable came in the first order in terms of the relative importance of the research variables. The results showed that the lowest total arithmetic mean was at the variable (soft driving) as it reached (3.56) and with a good level and standard deviation (0.654) and a coefficient of difference of (18.366) where the percentage of agreement on this variable

(71.22%) while the disagreement reached the percentage (28.78%), as this variable came in the second order in terms of the relative importance of the research variables.

Table -5- illustrates the summary of study variables

No.	Variables	Average sum	Difference factor	Concurrence rate	Non concurrence rate	Variable arrangement	
1.	Soft leadership	3.56	0.654	18.366	71.22	28.78	Second
2.	Business organizations performance	3.62	0.473	13.039	72.484	27.516	First

4. Testing hypotheses tested the first main hypothesis:

a. which stated that "there is a morally significant effect of soft leadership and its combined dimensions in the performance of business organizations from the point of view of the members of the research sample" as shown by table 6:

- The value of (F) calculated for the variable financial inclusion came what it values (202.769), which is greater than the scheduling value (F) of (3.94) at the indicative level (0.05) and this indicates (a statistically significant effect between the soft driving variable in the performance of business organizations) which It shows that soft leadership has an effective and clear impact on the performance of business organizations, i.e. the presence of leaders with a clear vision towards the changes in the organization's activities and its positive interaction with the opinions and proposals offered by employees will play an active role in achieving high and good performance ratios. The value (t) calculated for the marginal tilt factor of the soft driving variable (14.240), which is greater than the table value (t) (1.984) was recorded at the indicative level (0.05) indicating the morality of the marginal tilt factor of the soft driving variable. It is clear from the value of the marginal inclination coefficient (β) of (576) that increasing soft leadership by one unit will increase the performance of business organizations by (57%), and through the value of the corrected determination coefficient (Adju (R^2)) of (0.633) it is clear that soft leadership explains (63%) of the variables that occur in the performance of business organizations.
- From the results shown in Table (6), it is clear that there is an effective and fundamental effect of each dimension of the soft leadership variable separately on the performance of business organizations.
- In the light of the results shown in Table (6), we accept the first main hypothesis, which states that "there is a significant effect of soft leadership and its dimensions on the performance of business organizations from the point of view of the members of the research sample" at the level of significance (5%), i.e. with a degree of confidence (95%), which indicates that the variable of soft leadership and its dimensions effectively and fundamentally affect the performance of business organizations.

Table -6- illustrates the survey indicators for soft leadership analysis and its effect on business organizations performance										
Adapted variable	Dimensions of S.L			R	R2	ADJU	F	t	Sig	Decision
Business organizations performance	Vision	(α)	1.845	0.722	0.522	0.517	126.452	11.245	0.000	Accepting the hypothesis
		(β)	0.497							
	Connection	(α)	1.897	0.680	0.463	0.458	99.874	9.994	0.000	Accepting the hypothesis
		(β)	0.477							
	Emotional Intelligence	(α)	2.084	0.762	0.580	0.577	160.303	12.661	0.000	Accepting the hypothesis
		(β)	0.442							
	Soft Leadership	(α)	1.572	0.797	0.636	0.633	202.769	14.240	0.000	Accepting the hypothesis
		(β)	0.576							

Source: SPSS SOFTWARE V.25

B. Testing the second main hypothesis which states “there is a significant impact of the collective soft leadership on the performance of business organizations in the banks of the research sample.” As shown in Figure (4), Table (7) shows the statistical indicators among the dimensions of soft leadership in the performance of business organizations as follows:

- The calculated (F) value of the estimated model was achieved (67.598), which is greater than the tabular (F) value of (2.70) at the level of significance (0.05). Business in banks, the research sample, “at the level of significance (5%), i.e. with a degree of confidence (95%), and this indicates that the dimensions of soft leadership have an effective and essential impact on the performance of business organizations. That is, the dimensions of soft leadership have an active and clear role in achieving the performance of business organizations, meaning that the interest of banks and the endowment of its administrative leaders with all the qualities of soft leadership at the same time, this will have a positive impact on raising performance.
- The value of the Adju (R^2) corrected determination coefficient (0.631) shows that the dimensions of soft leadership are able to explain (63%) of the changes in (performance of business organizations) and the remaining (37%) are dependent on other variables not included in the study model. Figure (4) illustrates the impact of soft leadership dimensions together on the performance of business organizations.

Figure 4: The Impact of Soft Leadership Dimensions Together on the Performance of Business Organizations

Source: Amos V 25 Outputs

Table (7) Statistical Indicators of the Dimensions of Soft Leadership Together in the Performance of Business Organizations							
Multiple linear regression model using the method (Stepwise)				Multiple linear regression model			Soft leadership dimensions
Order of entry of dimensions	Sig.	t	β	Sig.	t	β	
2	0.011	2.574	0.170	0.011	2.574	0.170	Vision
1	0.000	4.061	0.255	0.000	4.061	0.255	connection
3	0.008	2.692	0.145	0.008	2.692	0.145	Emotional Intelligence
1.587				1.587			α
0.800				0.800			Multiple correlation value) R
0.640				0.640			Selection coefficient (R ²)
0.631				0.631			Corrected selection coefficient (R ²)
67.598				67.598			Value (F)
0.000				0.000			Sig.
2.70				2.70			F Table value
1.984				1.984			T TABLE value

Source: Program Outputs SPSS .V. 25

- Using the (Stepwise) method for testing the significance of dimensions, and after deleting the non-significant dimensions, it becomes clear that the model ultimately depends on both dimensions, i.e. (vision, communication, emotional intelligence), as the calculated (F) value of the new model was recorded (67.598), which is greater than The tabular F value of (2.70) at the level of significance (0.05), i.e. with a degree of confidence (95%).
- It can be seen through the t-test values for the dimensions (vision, communication, emotional intelligence), whose values are (2.574, 4.061, 2.692), respectively, are greater than the tabular (t) value of (1.984), and this indicates the significance of the marginal slope of all dimensions.
- It is evident from the value of the marginal slope coefficient of the vision dimension of (0.170) that increasing the dimension by one unit will lead to an increase in (the performance of business organizations) by (17%). It is also evident from the value of the marginal slope coefficient of the communication dimension (0.255) that increasing the dimension by one unit will lead to an increase in (the performance of business organizations) by (25%). It is clear from the value of the marginal slope coefficient of the emotional intelligence dimension of (0.145) that an increase in the dimension by one unit will lead to an increase in (the performance of business organizations) by (14%).

Fourthly: Conclusions and recommendations

1. Conclusion

- a. The results in the banks of the research sample showed that the variable (soft leadership) achieved a level of agreement that was good by (71.22%) and this indicates the use of managers in the banks of the research sample for the style of soft leadership, which mixes

emotional intelligence and administrative authority has an impact on improving performance in the bank.

- b. The results proved the existence of the impact of soft leadership in its dimensions in the performance of business organizations and this means that the leader has a clear vision sound and flexibility in dealing and his interaction positively with employees, will motivate them and improve their performance and thus will lead to raising the performance of banks.
- c. The results of the test proved the impact of the dimensions of soft leadership combined on the performance of business organizations that although all dimensions of soft leadership affect the performance of business organizations, but the dimension of communication is the most influential between them and this indicates that the interest of the administrative leadership in the banks of the research sample to communicate with different administrative levels and provide communication devices and exchange of advanced information, will lead to raising the level of performance in the bank.

2. Recommendations

- a. Attention to the enhancement of the dimension of vision by the management of the bank as it has come in the first place in terms of importance among the dimensions of soft leadership and this is considered a strength point on which banks should be based, and this is done by supporting the participation of different administrative levels in the development of the vision of the bank, which is characterized by comprehensiveness and creates motivation and motivation for employees to give their best.
- b. The dimension of communication should be taken care of by the management of the bank, where it came in second place in terms of importance among the dimensions of soft leadership and this is done by providing the necessary devices to help employees communicate effectively between the different administrative levels and exchange the necessary information that helps in raising the organizational performance of the bank.
- c. The management of banks to pay attention to the dimension of emotional intelligence, where it came in third place in terms of importance among the dimensions of soft leadership and this is done through the possession of administrative leadership in the bank positive social features that help to create a spirit of cooperation between employees and bank management and to be characterized by the ability to control their actions and understand the emotions of others in addition to the administrative leaders in banks help employees to correct mistakes .
- d. When examining the impact of the dimensions of soft leadership combined on the performance of business organizations, it was found that the communication dimension is the most influential dimension in the performance of business organizations, so the bank management should strengthen this dimension as a strength point, and emotional intelligence came in third place in terms of influence and this indicates the presence of Weakness in this dimension should be addressed by the bank's management.

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